

PRACTICES OF GREEK SCHOOL PRINCIPALS FOR IMPROVING SCHOOL CLIMATE AS COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

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Abstract:

According to the literature, school climate is perceived as one of the most important factors affecting the effectiveness of school units. School principals play an important role in shaping school climate. With his/her daily communication behaviors and administrative actions, he/she can create a sound climate and a positive learning environment which motivates teachers to work with interest especially on their teaching tasks. This article, based on selected Greek bibliographical references and international literature, presents school climate approaching it as a key communication factor related to a school unit's management improvement, as it contributes to shaping and improving the framework of interpersonal and collaborative relationships among principals, teachers, students and parents. Within this framework, Greek public school principals use school climate as a communication strategy for achieving management goals. Their situation and practices are revealed in this paper.

Keywords: school climate, communication, school principal, education, school administration, communication management

1. Introduction

Communication is central to education even though its positive outcomes are not always evident. The purposes of communication in educational affairs could be many but the most important is to communicate effectively. Within school environment communication happens constantly and repeatedly between teacher to student, student to student, teacher to teacher, teacher to parent, teacher to principal or administrator,

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principal to parent, or vice versa. Communication regulates every interaction taking place between members of a school community. Effective communication, however, is a true challenge for all education professionals and especially for those who wish to successfully communicate in order to shape and create positive relationships between school and society. Moreover, effective communicative behavior is vital to each learning organization, as it associates with democratic leadership, organizational networks, and conflict management. School principals have the challenge of running a school, dealing with student-related issues and maintaining a satisfied staff. Thus, effective communication is essential for a school principal who wishes to be successful in his job of creating and maintaining a healthy learning environment (Kowarlski, Petersen, & Fusarelli, 2007). In addition to what a principal chooses to do, he/she knows that, by including verbal and nonverbal communication skills into his/her practice on a daily basis, he/she can greatly improve his/her school's organizational structure, which in turn provides secure boundaries for students and positive reinforcement for teaching and other staff members.

Issues of communication in the school environment used to be defined as "Communication Education" (CE) or more widely as "Educational Communication" (EC). As Simonds & Cooper (2011, 2) claim, "*Researchers in the field of CE are interested in what happens in the classroom and how we develop the ability to communicate competently*". Also, Rubin (2011) claims that EC is an umbrella term that encompasses all speaking, listening, and relational constructs and concepts that relate to learning. Since the early 1970s, researchers have been interested in communicative characteristics of teachers that enhance or hinder learning; student communicative characteristics that increase or inhibit learning; teaching communication strategies that augment learning; how best to give criticism of student speeches; how best to evaluate student communication; how public speaking is best taught; and what should be taught in speech communication and media curricula and so many other related issues (McCroskey, Richmond, & McCroskey, 2006; Chesebro & McCroskey, 2001; Miller, 2000; Argyle 1988; Mehrabian, 1967). Interest in CE and EC issues rates constantly at a high level. More recent work has expanded to the effects of media on children, child development processes, and the use of pedagogical methods and newer technologies to facilitate classroom or distance learning (Johnson, 2017; Houser & Hosek, 2017; Powell & Powell, 2015).

Managing an educational institution is not something easy or simple. Managing an educational institution is very complex as it means communicating, conveying ideas, feelings, decisions to subordinates and the possibility of returning information. Thus, what is needed is deep knowledge of communication management and long-term experience in this field. Just as a teacher, who is able to communicate well with students, can inspire them to learn and participate in class, a principal who is able to communicate well with teachers, students, parents and administrators of education, can inspire them to contribute to the school running in an effective way. All school members and individuals need to communicate to share their knowledge and information with others.

Within this framework, this theoretical article refers to school communication management through the concept of school climate, its categories and the way it is influenced by school principals. As school communication management interacts with school climate, the authors' focus is on modern educational management in regard to communication which is considered to be a fundamental factor in shaping school climate and allow for efficient functioning of the school unit. The interest in this article is concentrated on the Greek educational system. So, the key questions of this paper are: Could the improvement of school climate be a communication strategy for better school unit management in Greek public schools? What are the usual practices used by Greek public school principals to improve their school unit climate? Do they use communication as a fundamental strategy for shaping the school climate of their school or not? The authors will try to provide the readers with answers to these questions based upon their readings of Greek literature and their personal school administrative experience.

As international literature claims, school is an organization in which the general purpose is the full cognitive, social and emotional development of students (MacGilchrist, Mayers, & Reed, 2004). However, in order to achieve its general purpose, the school must optimally utilize the human (teachers, administrators, staff, etc.) and the material resources (building, audiovisual media etc.) it has. In order to achieve these goals, the school must also have a good manager who will co-ordinate its human work and use its material resources, implement control systems and determine efficiency criteria for effective school functioning (McCarley, Peters, & Decman, 2016). Efforts to improve the quality of school units and increase their effectiveness are always at the heart of research interest, focusing on the manager's leadership role and the interaction managers have with other school members.

Especially in Greek educational culture, the school principal is the managerial person who has the legal obligation for creating a positive educational environment and ensuring smooth working relationships among school staff. Therefore, communication is considered by Greek principals to be the main strategy for school climate improvement. Collaboration between principals and teachers, effective communication among all members of the school community, sound school climate, and meeting the needs of the teachers constitute the background that facilitates the efficient function of a public school unit (Saitis, 2002). The communication practices and attitudes which are mentioned below and are based on the authors' long managerial experience and on selected Greek and international bibliographies conducted by eminent scholars, may provide the reader with further knowledge or practical ideas and/or a desire for further research of this subject. This paper will discuss theoretical issues about school climate, approaches connecting school climate to the managerial principal's role, and the use of school climate as a communication strategy for improving educational and administrative work and vice versa.

2. The concept of school climate: A synoptic approach

In order to approach the notion of "school climate", several definitions have been given, most of them converging. Thus, according to the Greek bibliography, the concept of "school climate" refers to the conditions prevailing in the school unit, to the "atmosphere" that is shaped, and also shapes, interpersonal relationships, which may be friendly or hostile, pleasant or competitive etc. (Pashiardis, 2004). Similarly, Saitis (2005, 135) states that the school climate is "*the atmosphere, the working conditions that exist in each school and can be pleasant, depressing, creative or repulsive.*" Likewise, Athanasoula-Reppa (1999, 140) states that "*the climate in a school can be pleasant and creative or depressing and repulsive.*"

In a deeper approach to this concept, Pashiardis (2000, 10) defines school climate as "*the whole of the dynamic interactions between the psychological, academic and physical parameters of the school environment.*" This is achieved when there is a balance between the external and the internal system of the school. External system means school hierarchy, such as the position of the principal, the deputy principal, the teacher, as well as the relationships established by their interdepartmental work dynamics. Internal system means relationships developed between team members in the workplace. In the end, school climate is the actual conditions prevailing in each school unit, which are shaped by the interpersonal relationships of all individuals who are involved in the school's function.

Usually, school climate contains an emotional aspect. It is related more to the emotional factor than to any other (Sotiriou & Iordanidis, 2015). School climate mainly refers to the quality of school life. Students, parents, teachers, school staff and school community members co-create school life. Rules, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, structures and infrastructures, teaching methods and learning practices have a critical role in shaping school climate. When a school unit operates in a communicative, collaborative, and democratic way, an effective school climate will be created which will motivate school members to work together in creating a safer, more supportive, and non-violent learning environment (Stamatis & Nikolaou, 2018).

From the administrative perspective, Pashiardis and Pashiardis (2001) believe that there are more factors that affect school climate. These factors are rules that regulate the formal school system, the informal style of the school principal and other important environmental factors that influence behavior, such as beliefs, values and motivation of the staff members who work in the particular school. Thus, within this climate perspective, are included concepts such as kindness, success, work, the manager's behavior towards teachers, students, parents, and vice versa, the way they apply the school regulations, etc.

Despite common perceptions, there are significant differences in the definitions given by the theoreticians about the concept of the school climate. There are, for example, those who claim that school climate is a set of characteristics that describe, unite and maintain the school unit and which influence the behavior of the people working within it (Brucato, 2005). Others argue that the school climate is the result of the style of

exercising the administrative function, organizational and other operational procedures that are being carried out daily in the school unit, that is, the way in which the school actually works (Kelley, Thornton, & Daugherty, 2005).

According to Hatzipanagiotou (2003), school climate has two dimensions: the “academic” and the “social”. The academic climate is a result of the way the school uses praise and rewards, the ability and effectiveness of principals and teachers, as well as cooperative processes. The social climate is related to student values, student participation in the school curriculum, rules applied equally to all at school, staff and pupils' support, as well as the general school environment.

Regardless of the above, the school climate is ultimately understood from a completely subjective point of view, considering that it is shaped by the school principal, the teachers, the pupils and the parents. At the same time, each member of the school community perceives the school climate in their own way, using their own criteria. Thus, it is very difficult for school members to understand what school climate really is and behave properly. For example, if a teacher believes that he/she works in a school with authoritarian school climate, it would be normal to behave and act accordingly, regardless of whether the principal of this unit does everything to be democratic and create a pleasant work environment (Nguni, Slegers, & Denessen, 2006).

Everyday experience shows that each school unit has its own climate, which affects the reactions and the way people work in it. In a similar way, the school climate, which is different from school to school, emits the specificity of its characteristics to the school where it is created and prevails (Kelley, Thornton, & Daugherty, 2005). Consequently, the individuality of the school exists because the climate of a school is formed by a multitude of variables and factors. Each school sets different priorities, choices and factors and this is a key reason why the school climate is what ultimately makes one school unit stand out from another (Tajasom & Ahmad, 2011).

After visiting several schools or based on personal experience gathered by working in a school one might remark that:

- a) in some of these, the principal, teachers and students can work with a lot of zeal and passion, not closing themselves, but sharing their problems, seeking solutions together for whatever might arise and concern them, between staff members as well as with the parents, working together harmoniously and believing in what they are trying to achieve,
- b) in another school, teachers may feel unhappy with their principal because he does not play the role of co-worker, mentor, facilitator, mediator with his knowledge and skills, but tries to cover his own inadequacy and weaknesses, abusing the power he has been trusted with,
- c) in yet another, “everything is done because it has to be done”. There are no goals and objectives, but some functions are performed to make everyone “OK”. At such a school there is apathy, a stagnant formality, no organization and no control. In all three cases, any relationships that develop between the members of the educational community at the workplace affect the functions of the school, are

manifested and perceived by pupils and parents and, of course, inevitably influence their behavior (Korkmaz, 2007).

To sum up, the term “school climate” is multi-dimensioned as connected to the well-being and happiness of students and staff. It constitutes patterns of all school community members and their personal experience of school life that reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices, and organizational structures. Schools differ in their climate type.

3. Basic types of school climate

According to McCarley, Peters and Decman (2016), there are three types of pedagogical climate, which are formed by the balance between the school's external and internal systems, as outlined above. With the balance between the external and the internal system, the following three types of pedagogical climate emerge: the formal-impersonal, the atonal and the formal-personal. The formal-impersonal climate is characterized by rule domination and crowding out of interpersonal relationships, resulting in the absence of personal communication and cooperation among school members. The atonal climate occurs when the external system is nullified from the inside. In this climate the school is maladministered, people do not have a clear awareness of their roles and responsibilities, ultimately neglecting the pupils' knowledge and skills. Finally, the formal-personal climate is characterized by the balance of external and internal systems, resulting in cooperation, understanding and application of modern perceptions in the school unit (Polychroniou, 2008).

It is clear from the literature that researchers describe school climate in a variety of ways, resulting in a disagreement between them as to the variables that determine the school climate of a school unit (Chirkina & Khavenson, 2018; Pashiardis, 2001; Conley & Muncey, 1999). Thus, the survey by Holpin and Groft (1963) which in their questionnaire investigates the verification of the results "*concerning the interactions between the teachers, but also between them and the school principal*" distinguishes six types of school climate, which are:

- The open climate. Its characteristic features are intense activity, methodical fulfillment of goals and meeting the needs of team members. There is no coercion but honest cooperation between principals and teachers. The main characteristic of this climate is the "authenticity" of the behavior of all members.
- The autonomous climate. Portrays an atmosphere where teachers have at their disposal a considerable degree of freedom to act in school. There is a high team spirit as the principal exercises little control and epitomizes the model of enthusiasm and zeal. There are no external threats or influence. Teachers have a strong desire to teach and students are motivated to learn. There is a close relationship between the principals, teachers, students and parents.

- The controlled climate. It is characterized as impersonal and is task-oriented, giving relatively little attention to behavior, aimed at meeting needs, while the team spirit is quite high.
- The familiar climate. Friendly relationships prevail. Members of the organization meet their needs but pay relatively little attention to social control compared to performing the task, while the team spirit is not high.
- The paternalistic climate. The principal implements most actions as a result of his personal leadership. It is characterized by little satisfaction that is achieved either in terms of performing the task or the needs, so the team spirit of its members is low.
- The closed climate. It is characterized by a high degree of apathy, low team spirit, cold and formal working relationships, resulting in the appearance of a completely ineffective school.

As was previously mentioned, schools differ in their climate type. School climate is one of the most significant factors determining educational achievement. The role of principal is critical to the shaping of school climate because he/she is the person who has the authority, the ability and the competence to behave in the appropriate way in order for the school to function properly. In a survey conducted by Kavouri (1998) on organizational climate prevailing in the Greek administration of education, four types of climate were revealed: open, closed, climate of participation / dedication and climate of abstention / avoidance. They were identified as follows:

- Open school climate. All teachers work together in harmony, have a sense of professional responsibility and the full support of the school principal, who is characterized by low level of direction and limitations.
- Closed school climate. The principal gives direction and limitations rather than encouraging and supporting teachers' initiatives, so teachers are indifferent to and distance themselves from school issues.
- Participation/dedication climate. Principals are open, collaborate and devote themselves to their work.
- Abstention/avoidance climate. The principals are not strict, they support teachers, but they are not devoted to their work and have a high degree of apathy.

According to the above, Kavouri (1998), studying the qualities of the school climate, focuses on the interpersonal relationships that develop in the school unit and measures the social interaction that is formed between the teachers and between the teachers and the school principals.

Similarly, Thapa, Cohen, Guffey and Higgins-D'Alessandro (2013), who studied the characteristics of the pedagogical climate, underline the importance of interpersonal relationships among school community members. This research focused on school communication relationships, mutual understanding and democratic processes developed among school community members, and concluded that all these aspects affect school climate in a significant way.

From what has been mentioned above, it is clear that any of the aforementioned basic types of school climate may be typically prevalent in a school. It is, however, the climate (subjectively) experienced by the members of the school that affects the way teachers communicate, work and, ultimately, the quality of their work. Living in a climate of harmonious interpersonal relationships and having good cooperation between school co-workers is bound to play a decisively positive role in the school's administrative and teaching functions (Kor & Opare, 2017).

Greek principals as they experience the ignorance of the significance of their role and as they work with lack of appropriate support, know that they could use the power of communication to best shape their school climate. They also know that success of teaching and learning at school does not depend only on the extent to which the teacher holds or on his/her knowledge or ability to apply modern teaching techniques, but it primarily depends on the degree of interpersonal relationships and effective communication they develop which will create a pleasant and positive learning environment (McCarley, Peters, & Decman, 2016; Stamatis, 2013). It depends on the quality of the school communication management established in the school unit as a result of the school principal's activities, choices, relationships and management strategies and on the school climate he/she gradually established.

4. The role of principals in shaping school climate and the role of Greek public school principals

Over the last few decades many researchers have focused their interest on study related to efficient school environment. Many of them conclude that leadership is the key factor in school effectiveness (Bush & Bell, 2002; Fullan & Hargreaves, 1998). Moreover, it has been evident that among all educational factors which positively contribute to school and learning improvement, school climate is next, following effective teaching (Leithwood et al., 2004). In today's time, effective schools undoubtedly are those run by efficient principals, according to the literature (Smith, 2012; Siccone, 2011). Furthermore, the research about the school principal role is consistently interesting as it is critically connected to the effectiveness of educational work and shaping of interpersonal relations among school community members. These relationships along with working conditions constitute the school climate.

The role of modern principals in shaping school climate is extremely important. Within the Greek educational system - as happens in many other systems all over the world - an efficient and effective school principal (who usually is called school administrator in US, headteacher in UK, director in Greece etc.) assumes the greatest responsibility for properly running a school unit. Nowadays, the necessity for school improvement and effectiveness is higher than before. Therefore, the modern role of a principal is very important and extremely complicated. A modern principal is required to undertake new, complicated and difficult duties, beyond traditional administrative tasks. A modern principal is required to become a leader in administrative and human

resources management issues, in issues of communication development, in interpersonal relationships management, in public relations, in teaching and learning aiming at consistent change for improvement and openness of the school unit (Stamatis, 2013; Fullan, 1991). All of these are aspects related to school climate.

Furthermore, within the Greek educational system the role of principal – especially in the public school - is extremely concentrated according to domestic legislation. The Greek school principal has a complicated and multitasked role. Under the title “*dieftintis*” (director), the school principal must function as administrator, manager, teacher, secretary, guardian, repairman, counselor, negotiator, judge etc. This role does not essentially allow the principal to undertake the role of a real leader within the school unit (Andreou & Papakonstantinou, 1994; Saitis, 2005a).

The Greek legislation seems to recognize the complexity and the importance of the school principal’s role as the leader of the school unit however, Central Education Authority (Ministry of Education) has not provided the principal with decision making “authority”. Consequently, a principal does not have the ability to receive initiatives for properly leading and immediately affecting the teachers aimed at effectively running the school unit (Saitis, 2005). The most important decisions concerning the running of a school unit are taken by the Ministry of Education. Therefore, a Greek principal is more of an executive staff member of school administration, a supervisor with limited authority, than a leader who has the power to autonomously run the school unit. Moreover, a Greek principal does not have the right to make changes in the functioning of the school unit he/she runs in such a way that differentiates that unit from others. Furthermore, the principal cannot make changes in the curriculum, instructional approaches, staff choices or even the assessment of educational work. The principal is obliged to obey the rules, directions or legislation set by the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs. Hence, the educational content is long-lasting, unchangeable, and absolutely the same for every school unit of the state unless it would be changed by the next government.

The principal’s work is characterized by great complexity. It is also very significant for the effective achievement of school goals. Despite these issues, the Greek state has not taken into deep consideration the importance of the principal’s role even for those who work in public schools. Actually, principals receive low support in their work from the local and central educational authorities. Principals are not properly prepared to effectively play the difficult and multi-dimensioned role required by the state. Furthermore, Greek principal’s education and training are extremely limited as there is not central and long-term planning for executive administrative staff of education (Gournaropoulos & Kodakos, 2003). What actually exists in the Greek educational system is only a short-term principal’s training which takes place within the framework of specific training programs mainly supported by the European Union. Nevertheless, postgraduate degree programs have developed during the last few years which offer courses related to educational administration, leadership and school management issues.

Moreover, in the Greek institutional framework of education concerning the choice of public school principals, there are various problems. As many researchers have claimed, the choice of school principals does not meet the criteria of modern administration and school management. For many years, the most valuable qualification for obtaining a principal's position was the number of teaching and administrative years held by the candidate instead of further pedagogical and school management studies (Polychroniou, 2008). These qualifications have currently changed with law No 4547/2018 which has not yet been fully implemented. According to this law, administrative and pedagogical studies constitute the main criteria needed to obtain the position of school principal.

It is obvious that under the circumstances mentioned above, Greek principals cannot effectively contribute to school improvement. Thus, what is needed are important changes based on the conclusions of a long-term and reliable study which must take place as soon as possible. Within the framework of education for the 21st century, the role of principal is becoming more complicated and demanding compared to the past (Levine, 2005). Therefore, in order for a school principal to be able to effectively undertake all requirements of his/her role, he/she must be well prepared, aptly trained and chosen from the educational authorities with reliable criteria based on suitable qualifications for the position he/she will hold. Principals need to receive greater support from the state. Additionally, principals need more opportunities to participate in continuing training and self-improvement programs. Such resources will gradually and positively contribute to the improvement of school effectiveness. (Green, 2000).

Based on what has been discussed in this paper regarding the role of the principal in shaping school climate and the barriers and limits put on Greek principals, one might ask, how do Greek principals manage to run effective school units? The answer to this question is that they use communication as a key strategy in everyday work. Communication is the main part of the Greek principals' work. Principals develop interpersonal communication strategies to regulate everyday educational and administrative matters (Saitis & Saiti, 2018). They solve disputes, arrange requests and allocate duties among teaching staff. Using a diplomatic communication style, they act as role models of proper behavior for teachers, students, and parents. The use of proper and effective interpersonal communication techniques creates the conditions necessary for a harmonious, safe, and fruitful teaching/learning environment. Interpersonal communication includes social interactions such as information exchange, discussion, free expression of ideas and opinions, talks, chats, multi-oriented conversations etc. Furthermore, Greek principals consider that the more effectively they communicate with school members at all levels, the better the school will function. They know very well that qualitative and strategic communication can create excellent school conditions that improve school climate and vice versa. Principals also realize that time spent on communication activities within their school is not a waste of time. On the contrary, that time is undoubtedly a beneficial investment bringing profits – sooner or later - to themselves and to proper school functioning.

5. Summing up

This article refers theoretically to the school climate as a communication strategy for better school management. It puts emphasis on Greek principals' practices according to the authors' extensive school managerial experience and selected bibliographical references from Greek and international literature. As can be seen from what is mentioned above, the type of climate created in a school is very important because it influences factors such as team spirit, satisfaction and the effective exercise of the schoolteachers' duties. The school climate affects not only the productivity of teachers and their relationships, but also the learning capability of pupils, their performance and their emotional and social development. An effective school requires a positive, non-violent and sound climate to ensure its smooth and efficient operation.

Open and effective communication between principals and teachers and all school community members is one of the most important factors affecting the school climate. The establishment of effective communication in the school unit is necessary and precious in order for principals to create and maintain a positive and sound climate. Thus, Greek principals have implemented interpersonal communication as a fundamental strategy for better achieving school goals of the unit they run. In this way, they manage to bring a good counterbalance for the lack of domestic legislation and other opposed factors which make difficult their leading role. They know by personal experience mainly and not by specific training that the improvement of school climate could be a communication strategy which might positively contribute to better school unit management and vice versa.

Within this framework, principals make communication the best instrument for achieving their managerial tasks. Keeping the door of their office open, they communicate in every possible and effective way with anybody who has a relationship with their school unit. They communicate constantly for any school matter, reason and purpose, without setting time limits. Consistent and unlimited communication is used within Greek school units as a basic managerial strategy to improve management effectiveness. Good practice of interpersonal communication as used within Greek school units may constitute a positive paradigm for the improvement of school principal effectiveness throughout the world, leading to many benefits in school functioning. It is not something miraculous, but it really works in many ways.

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